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Technical Efficiency and Profitability: An Assessment of the farm business survey¹

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Key message: Technical efficiency – the rate inputs are converted to outputs – will influence the economic and environmental performance of Scottish farms. We find that an average farm can increase farm net profit by up to 60% if best practice is optimised.

Main Findings

- The modelling results showed improvements in farm net profit by +65% on dairy farms, +50% on beef farms, + 70% on sheep farms and +80% on a cereal farm under a full efficiency scenario (Figure 1).
- In dairy farming system, farms with lower half of profitability were estimated to increase farm net profit by 3-folds whereas upper half profitable farms improved farm net profit by only +43%.
- Beef and sheep farms in the upper half of profitability were estimated to have a slightly larger increase (+81% and +42% respectively) in farm net profit compared to the farms in the lower half of profitability (+78% and +38% respectively).
- In cereal farming system, farms in the upper half of profitability were estimated to have substantially higher increase (+83%) in farm net profit when full technical efficiency was allowed compared to the farms in the lower half of profitability (+60%)

Figure 1: Average farm net profit under the baseline and efficiency scenarios for different farming systems

¹ This research was undertaken within the Scottish Government Rural Affairs and the Environment Portfolio Strategic Research Programme 2022-2027, Project SRUC-B3-1 – Ensuring positive behavioural change for farmers towards best practice for clean growth: economic and behavioural investigations.

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Introduction

Technical efficiency is critical to meet production, economic and environmental goals. We compare results from an optimizing farm level model, which assumes all farms are operating at best practice, with observed technical efficiencies from the farm business survey that show how far farms are operating from best practice as defined by observed peer group farms. This determines the economic benefits of achieving total technical efficiency by comparing current technical efficiency to a hypothetical scenario where farms utilize available farm resources to the optimal level with a 100% technical efficiency.

Methods

The farm level optimising model, ScotFarm (Shrestha, 2018)³ maximises individual farm net profit within farm resources. The Scottish Farm Business Survey (FBS, 2020)⁴ was used to extract farm level data from four major farming systems: dairy, beef, sheep and cereal farming systems. Technical efficiency (TE) scores for each of the farms in the FBS database were estimated (Barnes, 2022)⁵. The TE scores varied substantially across and between Farm Business Survey farms in dairy, beef, sheep and cereals farms in 2020. The Barnes (2022) work lists the drivers which influence farm technical efficiency. The ScotFarm model was run for individual farms in all four farming systems under two scenarios; i) a **baseline scenario** where outputs generated from farming activities of a farm were constrained by the observed farm TE scores; and ii) an **efficient scenario** where 100% TE is assumed, and farms generated outputs efficiently under optimal uses of inputs. The model output of the efficient scenario was compared with the baseline scenario to estimate economic consequences of technical efficiency on individual farms in these farming systems.

Policy Implications

Achieving a higher technical efficiency is economically beneficial to all farms. This can be achieved through adoption of best practice benchmarked against comparator farms. Some of the practices such as improved record-keeping and specialisation are realistic for these farms. This informs future policy thinking and shows the economic potential of best practice adoption across Scottish farming. Future policies need to be aimed at identifying and targeting these factors to improve farm efficiency to achieve green agriculture.

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³ [ScotFarm - a farm level optimising model — SRUC, Scotland's Rural College](#)

⁴ <https://www.gov.scot/publications/scottish-farm-business-income-annual-estimates-2020-2021/pages/12/>

⁵ [Scottish Farm Efficiency: trends and drivers from 1989 to 2020 — SRUC, Scotland's Rural College](#)

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